

CLASSIFICATION OF MILITARY-LEGAL ISSUES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF AMIR TEMUR'S ARMY (IN THE EXAMPLE OF TEMUR'S LAWS)

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Annotation: This article discusses Amir Temur and "Temur's Constitutions" during the Timurid period.

Key word: "Temur Tuzuklari" Samaerkhan, calligraphy, visual arts, music, architecture, brawler, tourist, ambassador, creativity, decorator, roads.

Along with famous scientists and statesmen, the past of the Uzbek nation is decorated with famous military commanders such as Mahmud Ghaznavi, Sotug Bugrokhan, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Babur, Shaibani Khan, Ubaidullah Khan the First, Abdullah Khan the Second. But the military-legal issues in the countries where these generals worked, excluding the period of Amir Temur, it can be said that very little has been studied. Military campaigns and military law during the time of Amir Temur attracted the attention of experts in this field, and some scientific works were written about it. For example, M.I. Ivanin, a member of the military-scientific committee of the general staff of the Russian Empire, wrote the work "O voennom iskusstve i zavoevaniyax mongolo-tatarskih, sredneaziatskih narodov pri Chingizkhane i Tamerlane" in 1836-1845. This work was published in a military magazine. The author completed and revised this work in 1874. The book was published in full in 1875 by the military-scientific committee of the General Staff in St. Petersburg. The main basis of this work was the "Tuzuklari Temur" and other historical sources. The military art of the peoples of Central Asia was introduced to be taught in military schools of Russia based on this work. 1 Since the

state of Amir Temur was a military-nobility state based on a medieval sole rulership, the main part of "Tuzuklar" was devoted to military law, and the same issues in the work attracted the attention of scholars. Timur's kingdom finally had a large army and its supply system. Temur himself was considered the supreme commander-in-chief, and in his absence, the vice-chief amir, amir ul-Umara, was in charge of the work of the troops. According to "Tuzuklar", five people received this title: Amir Khudoidad, governor of Badakhshan, Amir Joku, ruler of Balkh and Hisar, as well as Amir Iku Temur, Amir Sulaymonshah, Temur's son-in-law, Amir Muayyadlar from the Orlot clan. According to the rule, the people who received the title of Amir ul-Umara were considered to be governors of border districts, military and civil rulers of regions under their control. 2 At the next level were four beklarbegi. Amir Temur says that people's unity, unity, cohesion are of great political and legal importance. "I gathered brave and intelligent young men around me," he writes in "Tuzuklar". All of them had the same goals, opinions, words and deeds. If they decided to do something, they would not give up on it until they finished it." It is known that in our society, which is building an independent, democratic-legal state, ideas about the highest positions of statehood and their guidance are now being formed and developing. We believe that in improving them, it is necessary to rely on works like "Tuzuklar", which have been tested by the times. For example, Amir Temur praised the holders of high positions as "Khos ul-Khos", i.e. the characteristic of the special ones, in the "Tuzuklari" of Temur, and appointed three hundred and thirteen of his servants to the position of emir, according to the "Tuzuk of Emirship and Rulership". He says that they are people of pure origin, pure lineage, intelligent, valuable, brave, enterprising, alert, careful, and think things through. An emir, a high official must have so many qualities. Now, the other side of the matter is that one can expect everything from life, especially when a high-ranking being with such qualities is injured during a battle. The owner takes this aspect into account and appoints a deputy to each emir. At first glance, this is a simple matter for today, but the deputies are honored as "muntazir ul-amarat" - candidates for the emirate.

Therefore, they believe in the next day and work. Trust is one of the important pillars of statehood. Sahibgiron often repeats that if the emirs and high-ranking officials do not believe in the future, they will undermine the foundations of the state. He emphasizes that people who are worthy of emirship and rule have such confidence. He believes that only a person who knows the secrets of battle, how to break the enemy's army, who can lead the army into battle without losing his temper when the war is heated, and who can quickly repair a defect in the army ranks, is worthy of emirship and rulership. Amir ul-umaro, who can be his successor, considers a person who can command the entire army with pride and majesty and punish those who oppose him worthy of such a high position. The emirs were divided into emirs of 1-12 degrees, who, depending on their level, commanded 1-12 thousand troops and were subordinate to each other from the bottom to the top. During the war, they were considered the deputies of the amir ulumaros. Emirs of rank were the chiefs of Timur's special servants, and they were emirs who came from 12 clans who received the stamp. The rest of the emirs were from 28 unmarked clans and were simply referred to as emirs or ulus, district emirs. A total of 313 people have been awarded this title. If we look at the power of the emirs who have a governorship or governorship from the point of view of state law, where they were governors, they were also civil and military authorized persons. In the uluses and hokimitas, the administrative apparatus was formed, these bodies were more involved in the collection and distribution of taxes, judicial affairs, and the provision of the army. During the march, the emirs of the ulus and district had to collect one horseman from each tent (otov), one horseman from each two huts (kapa, chayla) and one horseman from each settled population. The structure of the army is based on the system of tens, headed by ten chiefs, hundred chiefs, and thousand chiefs. Severe punishments were imposed on those who disobeyed the orders of their superiors in the troops during the march. "The sentence of the commander of a thousand was imposed on the commander of a hundred, that of a commander on a commander of ten, and that of a commander of ten on his subordinates, and those who did not follow it were

punished." The duties of chiefs, both among the military and among the raiyat, consisted in punishing the disobedient, expelling those who failed to fulfill their duties, and electing others in their place. Amir Temur banned it because he did not like physical punishment, and he believed that the chief, whose power was weaker than the whip and the stick, was not worthy of the position he held. His instructions and opinions on military law are astonishing with their evenness and precision as if a necklace were strung on a string. According to the order of emirs, one of them was appointed viceroy to the other, the first emir was the viceroy of the second, thus the eleventh - twelfth emir, in turn, the twelfth emir was considered the viceroy of Amir ul-Umar, and he was the viceroy of Sahibqiran. As we read the following order, we witness that the genius of Amir Temur illuminated the deep layers of the essence of the matter. For example, he forbids assigning the work of a tithe to a centurion, and the work of an emir to an emir ul-Umar. But it is said that if any of the emirs is interested and asks for a job, he can be assigned a task. The system of raising them from the lowest level to the highest rank is also quite perfect: those who showed heroism in battle won the right to the rank of tenth in the first rank, to the rank of centurion in the next, and to the rank of thousand in the third. If one of the lieutenants shows bravery, the soldiers who were first assigned to the regiment, but who stood out in self-defense, were excluded from this. In "Tuzuklar", the system of military crimes and punishments in this regard is expressed in special rules: - "If any soldier turns away from the war and flees, let him be deprived of our favor; - if they were forced to retreat, let them accept the apology; - if he panicked, let them follow him; - any soldier who runs away after running a sword against the enemy and is wounded, let them praise him and note that he is wounded; - when he reaches the age of old age while serving in a military service, he should not be deprived of his honor and should not be demoted, let him get useful advice from them. In this regulation, we see that Amir Temur introduced allowances for soldiers for the first time in the history of military law: "-if a soldier is captured, do not kill him; "If any of my soldiers come to our shelter, let them trust such a soldier and cherish him,

because he was loyal to his master and saved the right to eat." 2 Such rulings and regulations did not arise by themselves, they all relied on Amir Temur's life experiences and were formed based on them. If a soldier oppresses his subordinates, that is, he goes beyond the scope of service, then the soldier himself is handed over to the victims. If senior and local chiefs oppress people of a lower level than themselves, it is stipulated that they will be fined according to their property beyond the scope of their authority. Here, in the first case, the cop can be punished as much as the victim wants. The big and local chiefs got away with paying fines for their crimes. In the second article of "Tuzuklar", that is, in the part of military law, special attention was paid to the rules of maintaining the army. It is permissible to accept this as a matter of course, because in order to maintain a centralized state, the strict and just application of military laws was the first and foremost necessity. What aspects are mainly paid attention to in maintaining security? This is in several "Tuzuklar", including; to keep a watch; giving ulufa (haq) to the soldier; payment to the police; increasing the level of soldiers and armor; procedures for granting ulufa to sons and grandsons; which is clearly expressed in the laws of giving gifts and gifts. Amir Temur puts justice in the first place even in the creation of rules for maintaining the Sipoh. When he prefers to call one servant from among ten people, he establishes it by law, and says that in choosing a servant, he will take into account his experience, justice, bravery and courage more than the other nine servants. He also says that nine people should choose the head of the ten. The above fair rules are also taken into account in the election of centurion and thousand. Amir Temur's policy of paying ulufa (salary) to the soldiers is a proof of his deep knowledge of the economy of his time. "Ordinary soldiers", - it is said in "Tuzuklar", - should be paid according to the price of the horse on which they are riding, provided that they fulfill their duties properly. The second is that the salary was assigned not because of his service, but on the condition that he could fulfill his duties. This is very important. Because the soldier must receive his salary honestly, then his food and drink are considered honest, only then he is considered to have fulfilled his duty to the

Motherland, obeyed the law and obeyed it. This is also strictly defined by law in "Tuzuklar". Now, the first issue is that each of the sipohs was given a salary at the price of a horse. At that time, the price of a horse was expensive, and money, whether it was appreciated or not, never affected the salary of a sipoh. Certain procedures were also strictly followed in determining the salary, that is, the salary of the tenths was ten times higher than that of their subordinates, that of the centurions was twice as high, and that of the thousandths was three times higher. The appointment of ulufa was not made to the farmer, but they received ulufa with the approval of the tenth head of the centurion, the centurion of the thousand head, and the thousand head of the emir ul-marо. "I ordered that the salary of Amir ul-Umara should be ten times more than that of his subordinates"², it is said in "Tuzuks", and also the salary of devanbegi and vizier is ten times more than that of amirs, yasovuls, chapovuls³, oarsmen's salaries ranged from one thousand to ten thousand coins, sayyids, scholars, virtuous people, healers, astrologers, storytellers, messengers, and historians were also paid according to their circumstances. It seems that Amir Temur greatly appreciated the work of ordinary people. According to "Tuzuklar", a salary of one hundred to one thousand coins was set for foot soldiers, servants, and cleaners.

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